

FIBER ROTATION OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE LAMINATE UNDER TENSILE LOADING

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Introduction

Fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites are gradually replacing the status of conventional composites as a preferred solution for the high-volume production and economical demands of aviation industry.

For the outstanding ductility of the thermoplastic matrix, this kind of composites can exhibit larger deformation which allows a higher possibility for the fibers to rotate during the loading. Fiber rotation is more influential in thermoplastic composites, several researches have put effort for exploring this effect by experiments or modelling, but it still remains a considerable challenge.

In this work, a tensile loading was conducted to a carbon fiber (AS4)/ thermoplastic Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) composite laminate. This study observed the specimen during the test and after fracture to characterize the damage mechanism, especially the fiber rotation. For the laminates under tensile loading, the interfacial features of $0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$ plies and $90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$ plies delamination are definitely different. A significant 'white stripe' is observed at the boundary of 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies when approximately 70% tensile strength is reached. The off-axis plies deflected under tensile loading, the rule of the fiber rotation direction follows the principle of deformation compatibility with adjacent plies.

Tensile Loading on Laminate

The side views of the specimen during the test are shown in the figures.

At the beginning, there is no obvious change in the side view of the sample. With constant loading, when approximately 70% tensile strength is reached, significant 'white stripe' is observed at the boundary of 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies.

The stripes appear and extend, eventually forming delaminations.

Fractographic Analysis

SEM fracture surface images are shown in the figures.

In 0° plies, the fiber exhibited tension failure wrapped tightly with the PEEK matrix.

In 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, materials broke in a matrix-dominated mode.

All the crack angles within the 90° ply are 45° resulting from the shear force plies applied by adjacent $\pm 45^\circ$ plies.

Fiber rotation

Fiber rotation between 0° and 45° plies

The yellow solid line represents the initial fiber orientation, while the dashed line shows the final fiber orientation of the off-axis ply ($\pm 45^\circ$), the yellow arrow indicates the direction of fiber rotation. The figures also show the loading direction with red arrows.

For AS4/PEEK laminates under tensile loading, the fiber orientation of off-axis plies will deflect, the rule of the fiber rotation direction follows the principle of deformation compatibility with adjacent plies.

Fiber rotation between 90° and -45° plies

